

MODELING NEW GRAPHICS PROCESSORS PROCESSING FUNCTIONAL PROBLEMS

**RAKHIMOV BAKHTIYAR SAIDOVICH¹, ALLAYAROVA ASAL
AKBAROVNA², JUMANIYAZOVA TUPAJON ALIMOVNA³, SAIDOVA
ZARINA BAKHTIYAR QIZI⁴**

¹Head of the Department of Biophysics and information technologies of Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan,

bahtiyar1975@mail.ru

^{2,3}Senior teachers of the Department of Biophysics and information technologies of Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan,

asalakbarovna@gmail.com

⁴student 1 – course Urgench branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan,

zarina2003@mail.ru

Abstract. The main function of graphics processors since their inception has been graphics processing. Subsequently, after it became possible to program the processing of model vertices and pixels of rendered three-dimensional scenes using special programs (shaders), the architecture of graphic processors changed significantly. After the advent of the first general-purpose programmable graphics processors (G80 architecture from NVIDIA, R600 architecture from ATI), it became possible to process commands not only for graphic data in vector form, but also to perform ordinary calculations for arbitrary data on a variety of special cores, while implementing data parallelism.

Key words: Graphics Processing Units, pixels, architecture of graphic processors, processor.

Introduction.

PRAM (Parallel Random Access Machine) is an idealized abstract model of a synchronous shared memory machine. This model was proposed in 1978 by S. Fortune and J. Wyllie [5] to estimate the performance (in particular, the execution time) of parallel algorithms.

PRAM assumes the presence of an infinite number of processors, each of which can synchronously execute various instructions on data in a shared memory, thus operating in MIMD mode [2]. If all processors execute the same instructions, then this model can be considered an abstract SIMD machine. This condition is met even if all processors perform different operations or a different number of memory accesses. That is why this model is idealized, because in real computers, these actions vary in time. Nevertheless, this model is suitable for creating, analyzing and comparing algorithms, taking into account the following assumptions [6]:

- 1) the number of processors in the machine is not limited;
- 2) each processor has equal access to any cell of the shared memory;
- 3) the size of the shared memory is not limited;
- 4) there is no competition for resources;
- 5) processors operate in MIMD mode.

To simulate algorithms on a PRAM machine, emulators were created that reflect the main features of this model [9].

It is obvious that the number of different variations of calculation schemes for the constructed graphs will have different possibilities for parallelization. Operations between which there is no path in the constructed graph can be performed in parallel.

Materials nad Methods Bulk Synchronous Parallel (BSP, Valiant, 1990) is an extension of the PRAM model [8]. Later it was transformed into a parallel computing standard [6]. In this model, the main attention is paid to communication and synchronization of processors. Therefore, the model consists

of the following components [7]:

- 1) Processors, each of which has fast local memory and can execute multiple virtual threads;
- 2) A communication network that allows sending and receiving communication messages from processors;
- 3) A mechanism for synchronizing all processors at certain points in time.

The algorithm in BSP has a vertical and horizontal structure [10]. The vertical structure is a sequence of supersteps, each of which consists of three main steps:

- 1) Local calculations on each processor using only the data that was stored in the processor's local memory. Calculations are performed asynchronously;
- 2) Communication between processes using a communication network (messaging);
- 3) Barrier synchronization of processes. Once a process reaches a synchronization point (a barrier), it suspends computation and waits for other processes to reach that synchronization point. the results of the program before sending them to the host (in conventional DRAM).

Unlike the G80, the multiprocessor in the R600 does not have a local shared memory, but consists of a certain number of vector processors. It is the number of vector processors that determines the size of a bunch of processes (wavefront - in ATI's terminology). In the best configuration, one multiprocessor included 16 vector ones. Each vector processor consists of four scalar processors, one transcendental function processor, a branch block and general purpose registers. Thus, at one time, due to the use of VLIW, five operations on 32-bit numbers can be simultaneously performed on one vector processor. But most general-purpose parallel computing emphasizes scalar computing, so this parallelization feature is rarely used. Different VLIW commands can be executed on all multiprocessors, but on one multiprocessor for all vector processors, the instruction must be the same, but with different address registers. Access to video memory is performed

for all threads simultaneously within 300 to 600 multiprocessor cycles [6], but due to the use of VLIW and scheduling of thread bundles, the delay in accessing the global memory of the video adapter is effectively hidden.

The memory controller reports to the task manager. Processed data and constant memory are stored in video memory and, if necessary, cached in caches of the second and first levels, while they are common to all multiprocessors.

The next architecture of R700 chips appeared in June 2008 [6, 8]. The main differences from the R600 were as follows:

- 1) multiprocessors now have local shared memory (16 Kb);
- 2) a separate first-level cache for data appeared for each multiprocessor;
- 3) the cache of constants and instructions is separated from the data cache;
- 4) the second-level data cache is divided into several memory controllers;
- 5) the number of multiprocessors increased to 10 in the best configuration.

ATI Stream SDK and the OpenCL language, which uses its own heterogeneous model [1, 8], are used to program ATI GPUs. Unlike CUDA, this model is applicable not only to data parallelism, but also to task parallelism, and takes into account the number of CPU cores. OpenCL is based on a C-like language for writing program cores.

Results and Discussion

The models of parallel programming solve medical problems discussed above are intended primarily for the programmer to have an idea about the main structural elements of graphic processors, which include memory and computing elements, and the relationships between them. In addition, both CUDA and OpenCL have some algorithm abstraction that assumes that input and output data are represented as an array of elements, each of which is processed independently of each other, due to which data parallelism is achieved. We highlight the main disadvantages of these models:

1) there is no mathematical description of the abstract model of the GPU, so it is impossible to estimate the running time of a particular algorithm on different GPUs;

2) significant parameters of parallel algorithms have not been identified, thanks to which it is possible to analyze and compare these algorithms in terms of execution time on a GPU with a certain configuration;

3) despite the fact that the models are heterogeneous (i.e. they take into account not only graphics processors, but also central ones), they do not have methods for making a decision about the target computing system;

4) for these models, general principles for optimizing parallel computing have not been developed (in [2, 6], optimization methods are given for a specific platform, but not for a model);

5) there is no general methodology for the development of parallel algorithms.

These shortcomings are associated with a number of factors that one has to face when developing a parallel computing model [9], the main of which is the lack of a formal parallel computing model using a central and graphic processor. A formal model is provided by all abstract models of parallel computing with their abstract machines, but it is quite difficult to find a formal model suitable for analyzing parallel computing on GPUs due to the diversity of their architectures. Nevertheless, there are attempts to formalize some aspects of parallel computing on GPUs.

Conclusions

Computer vision as a scientific discipline refers to theories and technologies for solve medical problems to creating artificial systems that receive information from an image. Despite the fact that this discipline is quite young, its results have penetrated almost all spheres of life. Computer vision is closely related to other practical areas [3]: 1) image processing, the input data of which are two-

dimensional images obtained from a camera or artificially created. This form of image transformation is aimed at noise suppression, filtering, color correction, etc.; 2) image analysis, which allows obtaining certain information directly from the processed image. Such information may include the search for objects, characteristic points, segments, etc.; 3) vision of the robot, designed to orient the robot in space by modeling the environment from images received from video cameras; 4) machine vision, which is used in production and industry for automatic product quality control, product defect detection, measurement control, etc. Typical applied problems of computer vision are [3,4]: This task is a continuation of the previous one, the result of which is an array of areas where objects can be found. The purpose of this task is to determine the presence in these areas of a specific class of objects that already has more specific features and, accordingly, can be better classified; Reconstruction of a three-dimensional scene from a certain set of input images (video stream) allows you to determine the positions of objects and a source in three-dimensional space, used to move robots, create panoramic images, etc. Tracking of moving objects in a video stream provides for direct determination of the position of an object in space by changing its position on two-dimensional images while maintaining the characteristic features of the object. This task is very resource-intensive and must be performed in real time, so the main emphasis when creating algorithms for this area is on their performance; Image processing. This task area is designed to transform the pixels of two-dimensional images and is a priority for other computer vision tasks. Almost all transformations are filtering transformations, i.e. a set of operations is performed on each pixel of the image, depending on other pixels that are in close proximity to the desired one using special matrices.

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